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The Effect of the Development of International Tourism on the Economy of Our Country

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Abstract: *This article describes the impact of tourism, international tourism and other areas of tourism on the economy of our country. In addition, the current state of international tourism in the world and in our country, the factors affecting it and ways of development are briefly covered.*

Key words: *Globalization, integration, foreign exchange earnings, international tourism, factors affecting international tourism, geographical factors, economic, political, social and demographic factors, tourist safety, World Tourism Organization.*

Currently, the process of forming a national model of tourism is being carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan. According to this model, the tourist market being developed in the country affects the socio-economic situation of the country like any market. It is considered an important tool in the development of cooperation between countries and in determining the level of investment and capital flow.[1] It is known that in countries with a developed market economy, mainly private and commercial companies provide services to tourists. However, under any circumstances, tourism can develop only if the state creates an optimal economic and legal environment.

The tourism sector is very important for the development of international relations of Uzbekistan. In the conditions of globalization, favorable conditions for the development of the international tourism sector have arisen in our country, and this has a great impact on the integration of our country. It is correct to say that it serves to raise the standard of living[1].

International tourism means tourism that crosses national borders. Globalization has made tourism a popular recreational activity worldwide. In this regard, several factors affecting the development of international tourism in our country were studied. They are as follows:

1. Geographical factors.
2. Economic, political, social and demographic factors.
3. Safety of tourists.

In addition, there are other factors that affect tourism. Due to the catastrophic impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on international tourism, the world economy may suffer losses of more than 4 trillion dollars in 2020 and 2021. This was reported by the UN News Service based on the report of the UN Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD).

According to the UN International Tourism Organization, during the first 10 months of 2020, international tourism decreased by 72% compared to the same period last year. Due to the travel restrictions introduced due to COVID-19 and the lower consumer index, from January to October 2020, the countries of the world received 900 million fewer tourists than in the same period of 2019. This cost international tourism 935 billion dollars. This number is more than 10 times more than the damage caused to tourism by the global economic crisis of 2009.

It is no exaggeration to say that international tourism has developed in the world since ancient times. According to scientists, the history of the formation of Uzbekistan's statehood began in the 2nd millennium BC and spans more than 3,500 years. International tourism has long been widely developed through trade and crafts. As we have noted, the emergence and development of international tourism leads to the establishment and development of trade relations, recreation and travel, as well as earning the history, culture, customs and traditions of the peoples of the world. There is harmony between them. This is also an important component of tourism. In these cities, which are the cradles of ancient cultures, in the early and later Middle Ages, the fields of science, education, crafts and trade were widely developed, magnificent palaces, mosques and madrasahs were built. In order to build such beautiful cities, not only the knowledge and skills of skilled craftsmen and builders were needed.

If we look at the experience of the world, a developed market economy includes not only the factors of production and exchange of goods, but also the market of various services. The main driving force of the modern economy is service.

Nowadays, international tourism is one of the most profitable and steadily developing sectors of the world economy.[2] According to the data of the World Tourism Organization of the United Nations and the International Monetary Fund, the tourism industry has already managed to outpace services, goods and other industries exported in the world since the year 200.

The role and significance of the "Great Silk Road" in the development of Uzbekistan's international tourism is limitless.[3] For several centuries, the peoples who lived in the east and East of this land were connected with each other by the trade route, which stretched from South-East Asia to the Mediterranean Sea and was called the "Great Silk Road". was staying

International tourism is an important sector for the economy of Uzbekistan, like other countries of the world. Most of the tourists visiting Uzbekistan travel on the Tashkent-Samarkand Bukhara-Khiva route. Because the tourism industry of Uzbekistan has developed in these places, and many objects related to the Silk Road have been preserved in these places. [4] Among the important documents developed in the development of international tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan in the following years is the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 2, 1995 "On Measures Regarding Uzbekistan in the Restoration of the Great Silk Road" and the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on measures to establish the infrastructure" announced for the purpose of implementing this decree can be included.

Until now, a number of companies have been and continue to operate for the development of tourism. The creation of the first tourism company in our country, the national company "Uzbekturizm" and the joining of this organization to the World Tourism Organization in 1993, was a huge step in the

development of tourism in Uzbekistan. New conditions and mechanisms have been created in the republic that are suitable for raising international tourism to a new level and for effective activity.

Today, there are several important recommendations for the development of international tourism in Uzbekistan:

1. It is important to offer a variety of activities and services to keep tourists interested and entertained.
2. Development of tourist sites in the country: It is very important to develop the reputation of tourist sites, cultural heritage, natural scenery and ancient cities throughout Uzbekistan and attract tourists to them.
3. Development of the tourism sector: You should develop the tourism sector by developing infrastructure, hotels, further improving transport networks and improving the quality of service.
4. Strengthening advertising and marketing: it is very important to pay attention to marketing strategies to advertise the tourist potential of Uzbekistan to the world.
5. Expansion of international cooperation: Cooperation with international organizations and receiving financial support will help you to provide services that meet international standards.

These recommendations will increase the development of Uzbekistan in the field of international tourism.

In short, tourism, which has a great impact on the economy of each country, can determine its political position. International relations and cooperation are closely related to this tourism sector. Today, a lot of efforts are being made to develop international tourism in our country. This is not only about economic benefits, but also improves cultural relations. At first glance, it seems that big money does not come from tourism, but on the contrary. In addition, in order to attract more attention of tourists, countries should not only have their rich history, but also be able to show this rich history.

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